

INFLUENCE OF COLLABORATIVE TEACHING METHODS ON ENGLISH LANGUAGE STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ONDO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698320>

Published Date: 04-March-2023

Abstract: The study focused on influence of collaborative teaching method on academic achievement of English Language students in secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population for the study comprised, students and teachers in secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was One hundred students (100) and one hundred teachers (100), making the total sample size of Two hundred (200) respondents. The respondents were selected through a proportional random sampling technique. The instrument used to collect data was self-developed structured questionnaire by the researcher, entitled "Questionnaire on Influence of Collaborative Teaching Methods and Academic Achievement in Secondary Schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria". The instrument was validated by an expert in Test and measurement, while its reliability, was done through test retest method and 0.66 coefficient reliability, obtained. Findings of the study revealed that teaching method could influence positively students' academic performance. Recommendations were made that; teachers should be adopting teaching method in relation to the subject-matter taught; teachers should endeavor to use teaching method that can sustain learners' interest in teaching-learning process.

Keywords: Collaborative, Teaching, Method, Academic achievement.

I. INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

In the educational sector of the nations of the world today, globally, there is a rapt and a swift attention to teaching and learning in educational sector mainly to ensure that pupils or students achieve a high academic performance. Hence, poor learning among students has been identified among other combined factors as challenges that are besieging the nations' education sector, Nigeria, inclusive. Oyekan (2004), opined that learning is the heart of teaching. What this bores down to is that the main purpose of imparting knowledge to the learners is for them to learn. Learning involves cognitive dimensions

the structural psychological, psychological the aspects of knowing as well as the whole chain of information process, such as the perceptual, the conceptual, the language acquisition, thinking, memory and intellectual capacity that is being used in the learning process. Also, to bring a relative permanent changes in organisms in a holistic context.

Oyekan (1994), explained further that learning is a gradual change in behaviour which need to be frequently practiced and reinforced to prevent extinction. Teaching is an intricate activity which involves imparting skills, knowledge ad values to the learners. It is a process of helping a child to learn fundamental concepts or processes and to things that will benefits him/her and the living community. It is a set of conscious and deliberate actions intended to induce learning by imparting relevant knowledge, creative skills and desirable attitudes required to nurture productive and responsible citizens. In a nutshell, the essence of teaching is to refine human behaviour, positively. Erinsakin (2016), contended that education is a behaviour changer and modifier.

Obviously, the avalanche of extant literature have shown that the level of teaching and learning in Nigeria schools at all level is not encouraging, thus resulted into poor academic performance of students. Adeyemo (1995), attributed poor performance of pupils to poor teaching method and learning styles of the pupils. Oyekan (2000), contended that effective teaching and learning is a function of a clear cut objective, meaningful instruction and guidance based evaluation. Further, it was stated that students' conceptual understanding could be enhanced when teaching is oriented towards the state of operational readiness of the pupils.

Kayode, Akande and Abdulrasaq (2004), stressed among others the following as factors that could affect learning; inability of students to link the new body of knowledge to their previous experience, poor motivation, aptitude intellectual capacity and low interest. Also, identified are; physical defects, mental retardation, fatigue and other psychological problems, school locations, family background etc. Erinsakin (2007), also has identified factors, such as; teachers' characteristics, poor communication style, poor teaching methods, poor classroom management and lack of non-availability of teaching aids or instructional materials couples with the teachers' inability to use them appropriately are some of the factors that are affecting teaching, thus resulting into poor academic performance of the students, particularly in English Language at secondary school level. Reports from different examination bodies such as WAEC, NECO, NABTEB etc shows the dwindling performance of students in English Language.

Teaching method of the teacher can also contribute to hinder effective teaching and learning process in English Language classes. Aderinoye (1997), explained teaching method as a particular way or approach used by the teacher to ensure that the stated teaching objectives are achieved. Oyekan (2004), further explained teaching method to mean teaching techniques which encompasses, using the relevant educational materials to enhance classroom management, learning and achievement of the students. Effective teaching method will facilitate meaningful learning.

Several researches have been out on factor that could often mar English Language students' academic performance, especially at secondary school level of education. These included; teachers' personality, classroom management, teacher cognitive level, teachers' motivation, school environment, family background etc. observable, little has been done on influence of collaborative teaching method on English Language students achievement. Moreover, the few studies that had been conducted were self-reported by the researchers without empirical validation. This observed gap motivated the researcher to carry out this study.

Statement of the Problem

It is truism that the hard core of any form of education is the teaching-learning process. Teaching is done purposefully to make learning to occur among the learners, which is a gradual change in behaviours; cognitive, emotionally, spiritually, socially, religiously, psychologically etc. In many educational system, globally, a lot of strategies have always been adopted to ensure that effective teaching-learning occurs. Specifically, in Nigeria, when it has becomes obvious that poor academic performance of students or pupils is not encouraging, based on the number if statistical reports in internal and external examinations across all levels of education in Nigeria, annually, particularly in English Language at secondary school level.

The academics and researcher have identified a lot of factors as being responsible for this ugly and unsavory trend among which are the teaching method that is/are being adopted by the teachers while imparting knowledge, skills and value to the learners. Equally identified is the students' or pupils learning style. Individual student or pupils has his or her prefer learning style, which could enhance or mar academic performance.

A lot of researches have been conducted on factors that could result into poor or enhanced pupils' academic performance. Observable, less have been done on teaching method specifically collaborative method. It is against this background that this study was carried out on influence of collaborative teaching methods on academic achievement of secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The study broadly focused on the influence of collaborative teaching method on academic achievement of English Language students in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated whether there is a relationship between collaborative teaching methods and subject-matter taught by the teachers.

Research Questions

Two research questions were formulated to guide the conduct of the study.

1. Will collaborative teaching method enhance academic performance positively?
2. Is collaborative teaching methods capable of sustaining English Language students interest towards learning?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were generated to guide the study;

H0₁: There will be no significant relationship between collaborative teaching method adopted and understanding of the subject-matter taught by English Language student.

H0₂: There will be no significant relationship between collaborative teaching method adopted and intelligence level of English Language student

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will be significant to the stakeholders in education in the following ways:

The findings of the study will provide justification for using collaborative teaching methods to teach English Language students in secondary schools in Nigeria.

Besides, the results of the study will serve as basis for the curriculum planners and developers to stress the use of collaborative teaching method by the teachers in teaching-learning process in the English Language curriculum for secondary school level of education in Nigeria.

Finally, the study will serve as a source of reference for researchers who will carry out study within the confine of the area of study in future. It will be made available to the public through, the internet services or Open Educational Resource (OER).

II. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The choice of this design was on ground that not everybody in the study population could be covered. Hence, sample of population was selected and data generated from the sample was generalized on the entire population of the study. It also afforded every subject in the study population to have a chance of being selected for the study. The population for the study comprised two categories of respondents, selected from secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The categories were students and teachers in secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Two hundred (200) respondents. One hundred (100) students were selected from ten secondary school in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria. Also, One hundred (100) teachers were also selected from the same secondary schools, these making the total respondents to be two hundred (200). The sample techniques used was a proportional sampling technique and random sampling technique through the use of ballot paper.

The instrument that was used to collect data was self-developed structured questionnaire, by the researcher, titled, "Questionnaire on the Influence of Collaborative Teaching Methods and Academic Achievement of English Language students in secondary schools in Ondo West Local Government Area of Ondo State, Nigeria". It was fashioned on Yes and No question (Pollar answer). The research instrument was validated by an expert in Test and measurement. The reliability

of the instrument was determined, through test retest method in which 0.66 coefficient reliability was obtained at two weeks interval.

Data that generated on research questions were analyzed through the use of descriptive statistics (Frequency Counts and Simple Percentages), while inferential statistics (Pearson Product Moment Correlation) (PPMC) was used to analyze data collected on the research hypotheses.

III. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: Will collaborative teaching method enhance your academic performance positively?

Table 1: Showing Frequency Counts and Simple Percentage on will collaborative teaching method enhance your academic performance positively

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
1	Can the collaborative teaching method adopted by your teacher influence your academic performance, positively	79	79	21	21
2	Collaborative teaching method adopted by my teacher cannot influence my academic performance, positively	88	88	12	12
3	Whenever, my teacher makes use of another teaching method, I often performed woefully, academically	80	80	20	20
4	The appropriate use of collaborative teaching method will improve my academic performance	72	72	28	28
5	My failure occasionally is caused by the use of wrong teaching method by my teacher	77	77	23	23

The findings on table (1) reveals 79 (79%) and 21 (21%) for Yes and No on items (1). That states that will collaborative teaching method enhance your academic performance, positively. On item (2), 88 (88%) and 12 (12%), obtained for Yes and No, respectively. While, on item (3), 80 (80%) for Yes and 20 (20%) for No were obtained. On item (5) which states that my failure occasionally is caused by the use of wrong teaching method. 77 (77%), obtained for Yes, while 23 (23%) gotten for No.

Research Question Two: Is collaborative teaching method capable of sustaining your interest towards learning?

Table 2: Showing Frequency Counts and Simple Percentage on is collaborative teaching method capable of sustaining your interest towards learning.

S/N	ITEMS	YES	%	NO	%
1	My teachers' wrong choice of teaching method does not sustain my interest to learn	91	91	09	09
2	My interest to always learn is due to the collaborative teaching method that is being used by my teacher	89	89	11	11
3	I hate to learn each time another teaching method is being used by my teacher	75	75	25	25
4	I can always learn better whenever collaborative teaching method is being used by teacher	32	32	68	68

The result from table (2) shows the responses on item (1), which states that my teachers' another choice of teaching method does not sustain my interest to learn. 91 (91%) and 09 (9%) were obtained for Yes and No. while for item (2), 89 (89%) and 11 (11%), obtained for Yes and No, respectively. For item (3), 75 (75%) and 25 (25%) obtained for Yes and No. Finally, 32 (32%) and 68 (68%), obtained for Yes and No.

H0₁: There will be no significant relationship between collaborative teaching method and understanding of subject matter

Table 3: Showing (PPMC) on there will be no Significant Relationship between collaborative teaching method and understanding of Subject-Matter.

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Teaching Method adopted by the Teachers	14.5102	1.4012	200	0.23*	.000	Sig.
Understanding Subject-Matter Taught	15.3104	1.5243	200	0.25*		

Findings on table 3 shows that there will be no significant relationship between teaching method adopted by my teacher and my understanding subject-matter, taught by the pupils. Since ($r=0.23^*$, $N=200$, $P<.05$). for teaching method adopted by the teachers and ($r=0.25^*$, $N=200$, $P<.05$) for understanding of subject-matter taught by the pupils. Therefore, Null hypothesis rejected.

H0₂: There will be no significant relationship between the teaching method and intelligence level of the students

Table 4: Showing (PPMC) on there will be no Significant Relationship between teaching method and teaching method and intelligence level of English Language students.

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	R	P	Remark
Collaborative Teaching Method	12.4016	1.4207	200	0.22*	.000	Sig.
Intelligence Level of students	13.4135	1.5304	200	0.23*		

Findings on table (4) reveals that there is significant relationship between teaching method and intelligence level of students. Since, ($r=0.22^*$, $N=200$, $P<.05$) for teaching method, while ($r=0.23^*$, $N=200$, $P<.05$) for intelligence level of pupils. Therefore, Null hypothesis rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Aggregately, findings on research question one indicated that the use of the appropriate teaching method could influence students' academic performance, positively. This agrees with the opinion of Oyekan (2004), that the use of appropriate method could enhance students' academic performance.

A panoramic view of the responses on research question two shows that the teaching method that his/her by the teacher could sustain English Language students interest to learn. This response was buttressed by Delta (1984) that, one of the major determinants of students' interest to learn is the use of the right teaching method by the teachers. Thus, the use of collaborative teaching methods has a positive influence on sustenance of students' interest towards learning.

The result on hypothesis one indicate that the teaching method adopted by the students could positively enhance understanding of subject-matter by English Language students. This agrees with Oyekan (1999), opinion that students' understanding of topics that are being taught by the teacher depending on the teaching method adopted by the teachers.

The findings on hypothesis two indicated that teaching method could positively influenced intelligence of students. The findings on table (4) agree with the opinion of Sarumi (2001), that teachers' choice of teaching method should be done in relation to the learners or students intelligence development. Further, it was stated that the use of appropriate teaching method could enhance intelligence performance of students in the teaching-learning setting. This also is in consonance with the opinion of Kassain t al. (2010) that intelligence development of students in any teaching and learning setting is a function of using the right teaching method.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers teaching method and learning style of learners could positively enhanced learners' academic performance. Also, that collaborative teaching method could positively influence English Language students' academic achievement sustain their interest towards learning, develop their cognitive level and also enable them to understand subject-matter taught in English Language, very well.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion of the study the following;

- i. Collaborative teaching method when find relevant and appropriate to the subject-matter should be adopted while teaching English Language at secondary school level.
- ii. Teachers should be advised to be using collaborative method to teach in English Language classes at secondary schools.
- iii. Teachers should be adopting teaching method in relation to the subject matter to be taught in secondary school.
- iv. Teachers should also consider the intelligence level of the students before adopting a particular teaching method.
- v. Teachers should endeavor to use teaching method that can sustain learners' interest in teaching-learning process, particularly in English Language classes.

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